

Investigation of Fuel Properties of Neem Biodiesel and Its Blends with Diesel

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Abstract— In this present work, neem biodiesel was produced from neem oil through a two-step process of esterification and transesterification reactions. The first step of acid catalysed esterification reduced the free fatty acid content of neem oil. The second step of base catalysed transesterification process converted the pretreated neem oil to neem biodiesel. Neem biodiesel is blended with diesel at various proportions. The fuel properties such as density, viscosity, flash point, and fire point of neem biodiesel (B100), B25, B50, B75 were determined experimentally and compared with diesel (B0). The experimental results showed that the density, kinematic viscosity, flash point and fire point of diesel fuels are lower than the biodiesel. Therefore, the density, kinematic viscosity, flash point and fire point of the blend increases with the increase of biodiesel concentration.

Keywords— biodiesel, neem oil, density, viscosity, flash point, fire point, fuel properties.

INTRODUCTION

Today, energy is an integral part of our everyday life. Energy is directly and indirectly used in commercial, residential, and industrial sectors. A large amount of energy required worldwide is presently developed from fossil fuels such as petroleum, coal, and natural gas. Fossil fuels are a major source of energy in today's world but due to the limited availability of fossil fuels and most countries are searching for alternative fuels to substitute diesel. Biodiesel is the substitution of diesel. Biodiesel is a non petroleum based fuel defined as fatty acid methyl ethyl esters derived from vegetable oil or animal fats. Vegetable oil can be obtained from both edible (palm oil, rapeseed oil, sunflower oil, coconut oil, sesame oil, peanut oil etc) and non-edible (calophyllum inophyllum, castor, jatropha, neem, cotton, rubber and mahua etc) oil sources. Table-1 shows the names of some important oil bearing species for biodiesel production. A broad variety of high free fatty acid content of vegetable oils is available in large quantities like jatropha, pongamia, neem, and mahua which convey great potential sources for biodiesel production in India. Biodiesel conversion is complicated if the free fatty acid level of oil is above 1% which will form soap with base catalyst and produces low yield of fatty acid methyl esters. A two-step reaction system consists of acid and alkaline catalyst is recommended for conversion of biodiesel from high FFA oils. Acid esterification process helps to reduce the free fatty acid level of oil and also prevent soap product during alkaline transesterification process.

Table 1: Oil bearing species for biodiesel production.

Category	Source of oil
Edible oil	Coconut, Sesame seed, Peanut, Palm, Sunflower, Rapeseed, Rice bran, Soybean, Corn, Safflower oil, Mustard, Olive, Pistachia Palestine, Opium Poppy, Amaranth, Apricot, Argan, Artichoke, Avocado, Babassu, Bay laurel, Beech nut, Ben, Borneo tallow nut, Carob pod (algaroba), Cohune, Coriander seed, False flax, Grape seed, Hemp, Kapok seed, Lallelantia, Lemon seed, Macauba fruit (Acrocomia sclerocarpa), Meadowfoam seed, Okra seed (hibiscus seed), Perilla seed, Pequi,(Caryocar brasiliensis seed), Pine nut, Poppy seed, Prune kernel, Quinoa, Ramtil (Guizotia abyssinica seed or Nigerpea), Tallow, Tea(camellia), Thistle (Silybum marianum seed), and Wheat germ
Non-edible oil	Mahua, Jatropha, Neem, Pongamia, Karanja, Cottonseed, Rubber seed, Linseed, Deccan hemp, Jojoba, Kusum, Orange, Sea Mango, Milk bush, Nagchampa, Tobacco seed oil, Algae, Halophytes and Xylocarpus moluccensis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ferenc L. Martinovic et al [1] produced biodiesel from waste cooking oil by single-step and two-step process. They concluded that the two-step process requires lower investment and produces biodiesel at lower costs compared to the single-step process.

Hossain A. B. M. S et al [2] manufactured biodiesel from waste soybean oil. The effect of different alcohol types on the yield of the biodiesel was investigated. Methanol, ethanol and butanol were used in this experiment. The reactions were carried out by using 0.5% NaOH, 1:1 oil to alcohol molar ratio for 2 hrs at room temperature. The results show that methanol gave the best yield, followed by ethanol and butanol.

Two step esterification/transesterification processes was investigated by Ramachandran Kasirajan [3]. Two step processes was carried out for biodiesel production from a non edible source of chrysophyllum albidum seed. Chrysophyllum albidum seed oil first undergoes an esterification reaction using H_2SO_4 homogeneous catalyst and transesterification parameter effects such as reaction temperature, catalyst loading, methanol-oil molar ratio, reaction time, and stirring rate were studied. The results show that highest conversion of oil to biodiesel was achieved as 99.2 wt% at the satisfying conditions of 1:9 molar ratio of oil to methanol, 1 wt% of KOH, and 500 rpm of mixing intensity with 40 min of reaction time at 65 °C.

S. Savariraj et al [4] investigated fuel properties of fish oil biodiesel and its blends with diesel. Three different fuel blends (25, 50 and 75% by volume blending with diesel) were prepared. The fuel properties of biodiesel and its blends were measured. Results indicated that the kinematic viscosity, specific gravity and flash point of biodiesel blend increases as the percentage of fish oil biodiesel increases in the blends.

Abhishek V et al. [5] researched viscosity, density, flash point and fire point of diesel, calophyllum biodiesel and its blends. The calophyllum biodiesel was blended with diesel by various proportions such as B0, B5, B10, B15, B20, B25 and B100. They reported that the density, viscosity, flash point and fire point increases with increase in biodiesel composition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Neem is abundantly grown in varied parts of India. The neem can be grown on saline soil, clay and alkaline conditions. A mature neem tree may produce 35–50 kg of fruit each year. Seeds of neem have 40-50 % oil. The fruit is a smooth, ellipsoidal drupe, up to almost 2 cm long. Neem fruit is green in colour initially and gradually turns into yellow when it is fully ripened. Neem flowers and fruits in tree shown in figure-1. When ripe, it is comprises a sweet pulp enclosing a seed. The seed is composed of a shell and a kernel. Figure-2 shows fully ripened neem fruits and neem seeds.

Figure-1: Neem flower and fruit in tree

Figure-2: Fully ripened neem fruits and neem seeds

Neem seed collection and oil extraction

The raw materials used to carry out this research are the neem seed. The fresh seeds are collected from Katharipulam village. The good seeds are selected and are cleaned, sun dried for two days. The dried seeds were taken for oil extraction through ordinary mechanical oil extractor.

Biodiesel production from neem oil

Biodiesel was produced from the neem oil by a two-step transesterification method. In the first step, the neem oil was poured into the reaction flask and heated. Then the mixture of methanol and sulphuric acid (1% H_2SO_4 based on oil weight) is poured into the reaction flask slowly. The mixture of neem oil, methanol, and sulphuric acid was allowed to react in the reactor at 60 °C for 1 hour under the stirrer speed of 350 rpm approximately. The reaction was stopped after 1 hour. After the reaction, the mixture was allowed to settle for 2 hours. After 2 hours, the two layers were formed from mixture. The upper layer is acid layer and the lower layer is esterified neem oil. The esterified neem oil was used to base transesterification.

In the second step, the esterified neem oil is taken in a reaction flask and heated to 60°C for about 10 minutes with continuous stirring. Then the methoxide mixture containing methanol and sodium hydroxide is poured into a reaction flask. The reaction was allowed to take place at a temperature of 60 °C and stirrer speed of 350 rpm for 1 hour. After the reaction, the mixture was transferred into separating funnel and was kept overnight to settle. The layer on the top is the biodiesel, while the bottom layer is the glycerin. The upper layer of the neem biodiesel was separated from the lower layer then the neem biodiesel was washed with warm water. After the washing, the neem biodiesel was subjected to a heating at 100°C to remove excess alcohol and water.

Preparation of samples

The blends of biodiesel and diesel were prepared in glass container at ambient temperature. The homogeneity of the fuels was achieved by rotating agitator at medium speed for 12 minutes. The percentage of samples is given in table-2. The fuel blends in this report were labeled as BX, where B represents biodiesel and X represents the volume percentage of biodiesel in each fuel blend.

Table -2: Percentages of biodiesel and diesel fuel used in preparing samples

Biodiesel Blend	Percentage of Biodiesel (%)	Percentage of Diesel (%)
B0	0	100
B25	25	75
B50	50	50
B75	75	25
B100	100	0

Apparatus and Measurements

Properties of the biodiesel and its blends were determined on different apparatus. Table-3 shows the list of the apparatus on which properties were tested and determined.

Table-3: Apparatus used for determination the properties

Properties	Apparatus
Density	Weighing balance
Kinematic viscosity	Redwood viscometer
Flash and fire point	Open cup apparatus

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fuel properties of the diesel, biodiesel and its blends were tested. Table-4 shows the fuel properties of diesel, neem biodiesel and its blends.

Table 4: Fuel properties of diesel, biodiesel and its blends

Property	B0	B25	B50	B75	B100
Density (kg/m^3)	812	827	842	857	871
Kinematic viscosity (cSt)	3.31	3.77	4.27	4.76	5.20
Flash point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	52	83	115	156	178
Fire point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	57	90	124	167	191

Density

Figure-3: Density of diesel, biodiesel and its blends

Density is the weight of a unit volume of fluid. Density is an important biodiesel parameter, with impact on fuel quality. The relationship between density and percentages of biodiesel in the samples is depicted in figure-3. As can be observed in figure-3, the density of fuel types increased as the biodiesel content increased in the blends. The density of biodiesel (B100) is 1.072 times that of diesel (B0). The density of biodiesel is normally higher than diesel, because the density of biodiesel is dependent on its fatty acid composition, molar mass, purity, water content, and temperature. R. Suresh [6] investigated the effects of blending on the fuel properties of diesel and calophyllum inophyllum biodiesel. Three different fuel blends (30, 50 and 70% by volume blending with diesel) were prepared. The density of biodiesel and its blends were measured at room temperature. The experimental results showed that the density of biodiesel blends increases as the percentage of calophyllum inophyllum biodiesel increases in the blends due to the higher values of biodiesel than that of diesel. Mushtaq Ahmad et al [7] prepared biodiesel from hemp seed oil by transesterification process. The hemp biodiesel was blended with diesel by various percentages such as B0, B10, B20, B50 and B100. The blends were prepared on a volume basis. The results showed that the

density of diesel fuels (B0) is lower than the hemp biodiesel (B100). Therefore, the density of the blend increases with the increase of biodiesel concentration.

Kinematic Viscosity

Figure-4: Kinematic viscosity of diesel, biodiesel and its blends

Kinematic viscosity is a measure of a fluid's internal resistance to flow under gravitational forces. The kinematic viscosity of the different blends of diesel and neem biodiesel in varying proportions from 0 to 100% (diesel to 100 % biodiesel) are shown in figure-4. The kinematic viscosity of B100 is higher than those of the fuel types (B25, B50 and B75) and B0. It can be noticed that neem biodiesel (B100) produced the maximum kinematic viscosity while pure diesel produced the least. The blends showed the intermediate results. The kinematic viscosity of biodiesel (B100) is 1.57 times that of diesel (B0). Osman Gokdogan et al [8] investigated the thermophysical properties of biodiesel (from castor oil) and its blends. Nine different fuel blends (2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60 and 75% by volume blending with diesel) were prepared. The results showed that the kinematic viscosity of biodiesel blends increases as the percentage of castor oil biodiesel increases in the blends. Ertan Alptekin et al [9] produced biodiesel from canola oil by a transesterification process. Biodiesel was blended with the diesel fuels at 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 50% and 75% on a volume basis. The fuel properties of this biodiesel were tested. They conclude that the kinematic viscosity increases with increase in biodiesel composition.

Flash Point

Figure-5: Flash point of diesel, biodiesel and its blends

Flash point refers to the minimum temperature at which a vapor can ignite when exposed to an external heat source, such as a spark or flame, and in the presence of air. The variation of flash point and neem biodiesel blends is depicted in figure-5. The relation between flash point and the percentage of biodiesel in the sample shows increase the flash point as the percentage of biodiesel increases in the sample, this because neem biodiesel is more flash point than diesel. The flash point of biodiesel is 3.42 times that of diesel. Laura aguado deblas his group [10] investigated the effects of volume fraction of biodiesel and

diesel on the properties of blends. Two types of biodiesel were examined: sunflower oil-based biodiesel and castor oil based biodiesel. Twelve samples of the two types of biodiesel–diesel fuel blends were created by blending 0% (B0), 20% (B20), 40% (B40), 60% (B60), 80% (B80), and 100% (B100) of biodiesel with conventional diesel fuel to produce the corresponding blends for experimental purposes. The results showed that the flash points of biodiesel–diesel fuel blend increased as the percentage of biodiesel increased. Olatunde A. Oyelaran et al [11] investigated fuel and physiochemical properties of mango (*Mangifera indica*) seed biodiesel and its blends with diesel. Blends at proportions of 10% (B10), 20% (B20) and 30% (B30) on volume basis were prepared. Results indicated that the flash points of biodiesel–diesel fuel blend increased as the percentage of mango seed biodiesel increased.

Fire Point:

Figure-6: Fire point of diesel, biodiesel and its blends

The fire point of a fuel is the lowest temperature at which the vapour of that fuel will continue to burn for at least five seconds after ignition. The fire point is always observed to be higher than flash point by around 5 to 14°C. The fire point of diesel, biodiesel and their blends are plotted in figure-6. It is clearly shown that the rise of the biodiesel content in the fuel blend increases the fire point of the fuel. The fire point of biodiesel is 3.35 times that of diesel. Pradeep N R et al [12] investigated the fuel properties of biodiesel from pupae oil and its blends. The blends of the biodiesel are formed in volume proportions of 10, 15, 17, 20, 23, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 % with commercial diesel. The various physical and the chemical properties of these biodiesel and its blends with diesel were measured. Experimental results show that the fire point increases with increase in biodiesel composition. Tamilvanan Ayyasamy et al [13] researched the properties of diesel and tamanu oil biodiesel. Experimentations were conducted on six samples on the basis of volume % for tamanu oil biodiesel and diesel blends in the step of 20 varying from 0% (diesel) to 100% (biodiesel). They conclude that the values of fire point of biodiesel blends increases as the percentage of tamanu oil biodiesel increases in the blends.

CONCLUSION

In the present investigation, biodiesel was produced from neem oil and was blended with diesel fuel. Then fuel properties of B100, B75, B50, B25 and diesel fuel were investigated. The density, kinematic viscosity, flash point and fire point of diesel fuels are lower than the neem biodiesel. The values of density, kinematic viscosity, flash point and fire point of biodiesel blends increases as the percentage of biodiesel increases in the blends.

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